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Author for correspondence:

J.R. Romero-Arias

e-mail: romero@mym.iimas.unam.mx

Supplementary Material: A mathematical model for pancreatic cancer during intraepithelial neoplasia

Joshua Briones-Andrade¹, Guillermo Ramírez-Santiago²,
J. Roberto Romero-Arias³

¹ Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Ciudad de México, Mexico

² Instituto de Matemáticas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Juriquilla Querétaro, Mexico

³ Instituto de Investigaciones en Matemáticas Aplicadas y en Sistemas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Ciudad de México, Mexico

Cancer is the result of complex interactions of intrinsic and extrinsic cell processes, which promote sustained proliferation, resistance to apoptosis, reprogramming and reorganization. The evolution of any type of cancer emerges from the role of the microenvironmental conditions and their impact of some molecular complexes on certain signalling pathways. The understanding of the early onset of cancer requires a multiscale analysis of the cellular microenvironment. In this paper, we analyse a qualitative multiscale model of pancreatic adenocarcinoma by modelling the cellular microenvironment through elastic cell interactions and their intercellular communication mechanisms, such as growth factors and cytokines. We focus on the low-grade dysplasia (PanIN 1) and moderate dysplasia (PanIN 2) stages of the pancreatic adenocarcinoma. To this end we propose a gene regulatory network associated with the processes of proliferation and apoptosis of pancreatic cells and its kinetics in terms delayed differential equations to mimic cell development. Likewise, we couple the cell cycle with the spatial distribution of cells and the transport of growth factors to show that the adenocarcinoma evolution is triggered by inflammatory processes. We show that the oncogene RAS may be an important target to develop anti-inflammatory strategies that limit the emergence of more aggressive adenocarcinomas.

Supplementary Material

Gene regulatory network

Gene regulatory networks (GRNs) are build based on the biological regulation of complex biomolecular interactions in tissues that consider the role of specialized cells and generally the cellular microenvironment. In the case of pancreatic cancer, a GRN has been identified from the activity of pancreatic cancer cells (PCCs) and pancreatic stellate cells (PSCs), as well as on the interactions between cytokines and growth factors that communicate between them [1]. On the other hand, network motifs in the GRN are important biological structures that describe cascade regulation and feedback between its agents and their behavior can be analysed through Boolean, stochastic, continuous, or delayed dynamics [2-7].

In particular, it has been shown that delayed dynamics play a key role in the description of the dynamics of these genetic networks. It can be used to further understand biological changes as it offers a more complete and detailed view of GRN behavior [1, 7]. We take as a starting point the GRN proposed by D. Plaucher, et.al. [1], where the most relevant genes and molecules in the expression and suppression of signaling pathways related to pancreatic cancer were identified. To understand the underlying mechanisms that arise from hyperplasia or dysplasia we consider a simpler GRN version that contemplates only the stable states related to the apoptosis and proliferation phenotypes of pancreatic stellate cells and cancer cells. We have deleted some interactions and focused only on the birth and death processes that can lead to tissue inflammation. The simplification of the GRN introduces temporal delays in the dynamics of the pancreatic cancer main regulatory genes, however, the stability of the original GRN remains unchanged so that the genetic dynamics of the simplified GRN yields information about the cell cycle in early PanIN 1 and PanIN 2 stages of pancreatic cancer.

The reduced GRN (R-GRN) of pancreatic cancer presented in figure 2 in the main text contains the actions of the cytokines TNF α and TGF β 1, which act as regulators and repressors of genes in PSCs and PCCs that culminate in observable phenotypes, such as proliferation, migration, activation, apoptosis and autophagy. In addition, in the apoptosis of cancerous pancreatic cells, the R-GRN considers the caspases (CASPs) as inflammatory response agents and apoptosis processes in cancer cells. Additionally, the R-GRN considers as the main genetic agent the RAS gene, since clinical data in pancreatic cancer show that in all PDAC and PanINs cases, this gene is overexpressed as compared to healthy individuals [8–13]. The R-GRN uses the interactions of the P53 tumor suppressor gene, the P21 gene as CDK inhibitor that acts as checkpoint protein in the G1 cell cycle phase. The EKR extracellular kinases participates in multiple cellular processes such as proliferation, differentiation, and regulation of transcription. Also, the R-GRN contains the BCL-XL gene that regulates cell death and the PIP3 gene that causes translocation of glucose transporters to the plasma membrane and glucose uptake into tissues.

Note that the KRAS gene is an essential part of the control, as it affects both, healthy stellate cells and cancer cells equally. However, the evolution in both cell types is different. Therefore, in order to distinguish the properties of each cell and improve the precision of the experimental evidence, it is convenient to introduce a feedback with a time delay that simulates the interaction of the RAS gene with the entire GRN. Considering these observations we have introduced a free parameter τ that represents the time delay. It will play a crucial role when calibrating the clinical activation times between the different states of the PanIN processes. Thus, the value of τ mimics the temporal progression of pancreatic cancer, from PanIN 1 to PanIN 3

onset, and provides a better correspondence to apoptosis processes in cancer cells.

Voronoi diagrams

Voronoi diagrams are a set of points assigned to a limited geometric region of space in the form of a convex polygon. Voronoi cells are currently used in many fields of science, however, it was Honda [14] who first proposed their use for modeling biological cells. To model the pancreas geometric shape and cell growth we define a geometric space domain as follows: 1) We build two regular shapes with points inside two rectangles that are connected by a double semicircular arc. This arrangement mimics a structure like a horseshoe that will help us to simulate the pancreas inflammatory process in the ductal and acinar cells. The extracellular matrix that surrounds the pancreas tissue is represented by a set of equidistantly separated fixed exterior points. 2) Because the points on the edge cannot define a convex polygon the associated spatial cells will not be closed so that they are not considered in the tissue development under consideration. 3) We randomly place N points inside the domain such that all Voronoi cells are closed and connected. To guarantee this, we use the Delaunay triangulation algorithm.

The spatial cells areas (A_i) vary in size and shape, and that the generated points (r_i) shown in the figure often times do not correspond to the center of mass of the corresponding biological cells (r_{0_i}). In a homogenization process, the average area $A_0 = \sum_{i=1}^N A_i/N$ would be the space that each one of the biological cells would occupy. In addition, we observe that the spatial cell distribution forms a regular hexagonal network, which is the network that produces the closest packed structure. In such a case, the distance in the regular array is $d_i = |r_i - r_{0_i}| = 0$, for all values of i . To emulate the inflammation processes we complement this two dimensional geometric model by introducing an elastic potential function $V(\vec{r}_i, t)$ with minima at the equilibrium points configuration r_{0_i} .

Mechanical fields

In most tissues, cells attach mechanically to their neighbors through their common interfaces and exert forces upon each other as well as on their surrounding environment. These complex interactions can lead to significant morphogenetic deformations that can lead to alterations in the developing tissue. These deformations can generate crucial folding, stretching or constrictions to establish and define the shape of the organism. Understanding how cells collectively perform these tasks is an important question that lies at the interface of physics, developmental biology, and particularly cancer initiation. Tissue deformation occurs when some mechanical properties of cells change.

On the other hand, cell division and apoptosis also impose physical constraints on the surrounding environment. Because of this, it is important to understand the mechanical forces that act on a tissue and how

equilibrium is reached. Bearing this in mind we consider the relevant internal and external forces acting on the tissue that balance the friction and viscous forces. Previous models have used springs and vertex models to understand how the complex interplay between cell shape, forces and mechanical constraints are generated within epithelial cells [15] and make epithelial tissues confluent with active matter dynamics as well as complex phenomena arising from other biophysical and mechano-transduction signaling [16–19].

In the present model, we use the average cell area, A_0 , as a measurable quantity to identify healthy cells. Any deviation from A_0 will point to an unhealthy cell. Experimental studies have suggested that inflammation may happen up to 50% of the size of healthy cells [20–22]. Here we have considered unhealthy cells when the average area changes around 10%. In addition, we consider that when cells in the tissue are isotropically shaped a non-zero distance d_i value will ensue as an indication that cells in the tissue are stressed.

To incorporate in the model the elastic properties of cells and tissue a deformation force is introduced by means of a harmonic potential [16] for the i -th cell that depends on its area A_i and its center of mass position, \vec{r}_i , as

$$V_i(\vec{r}_i, t) = \frac{K_v}{2}(A_i(t) - A_0(t))^2 + \frac{K_c}{2}|\vec{r}_i(t) - \vec{r}_{0_i}(t)|^2 \quad (\text{A } 1)$$

where the coefficients K_v and K_c represent the elastic constants and r_{0_i} represents the center of mass of the i -th biological cell. That is, the elastic potential energy is approximated to second order in the deformation by a Taylor series around the equilibrium biological cell state, (A_0, \vec{r}_{0_i}) .

At this point it is important to recall that biological as well as biophysical systems do not conserve energy. On the contrary, they undergo irreversible processes that consume and dissipate energy [23]. Taking this into account we have also included in the model a dissipation term in the form of a friction force, which for simplicity, we assume it is proportional to biological cell velocity, $-k\vec{v}_i$. It emulates the biological cell inability to undergo drastic mechanical deformations in shape and/or changes in size. Bearing in mind all the aspects of the above description, one can write down the following equations of motion for the i -th biological cell[16]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\vec{v}_i}{dt} &= -\nabla V_i - k\vec{v}_i \\ \frac{d\vec{r}_i}{dt} &= \vec{v}_i \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A } 2)$$

where \vec{r}_i and \vec{v}_i are the position and velocity of the i -th biological cell in the tissue, respectively.

We now turn to the emulation of cell proliferation (cell mitosis) and apoptosis processes. One should recall that the construction of a Voronoi diagram associates a polygonal form to each point of the population [24, 25]. Thus, cell mitosis requires that we choose two points inside a Voronoi

spatial cell. In each iteration the Voronoi diagrams are recalculated locally and the physical space is increased to make room for the two daughter cells until they reach the average size A_i . On the other hand, to emulate the apoptosis process a biological cell disappears so that the point associated to it is erased and the Voronoi diagrams are rebuilt locally.

Glucose transport

Several studies [26–28] suggest that cancer cells development is strongly dependent on glucose consumption since it drives the process of aerobic glycolysis. This in turn generates a greater production of cellular metabolites, which are necessary for the generation of new biomass and nutrients for the diverse signalling processes. Thus, increased glucose metabolism during cancer development is an indication that cancer cells prefer the use of glycolysis as a mean to generate ATP even in the presence of oxygen. By contrast, normal cells metabolize glucose for energy production and resort to the glycolytic pathway under anaerobic conditions [27].

Glucose transport across the plasma membrane is a rate-limiting step in glucose metabolism and is mediated by a family of glucose transporters (GLUTs) [29, 30]. GLUTs allow bidirectional transport of glucose across the cell membrane down its concentration gradient. This metabolic regulation facilitates its incorporation into the biomass of essential nutrients for cell proliferation. There are studies which show that the deregulation of this metabolic pathway in the presence of growth factors, insulin, and stress, leads to alterations in cell differentiation and transformation conditions [27, 31]. It has also been found in different types of cancer that GLUTs are deregulated and can be identified with some cancer expression patterns and the activation of certain oncogenes, for instance, c-MYC, RAS and SRC [32, 33].

Taking into account all the above information, one can surmise that the elastic field drives glucose transport through the cell membrane so that it diffuses elsewhere. One can assume that the amount of biomass transported per unit time from cell i is modeled with the Darcy's law of porous medium. Thus, we can assume that the membrane has a permeability that is proportional to glucose concentration gradient, ∇c , while the magnitude of potential gradient plays the role of the pressure gradient.

Then, expressing the gradients as finite difference, one can write down the following kinetic equation [16]

$$\frac{dc_i}{dt} = \sum_{m=1}^M l_{i,m}(c_i - c_m)|V_i - V_m|, \quad (\text{A } 3)$$

where $l_{i,m}$ is the contact perimeter between biological cells i and m and the sum is over all neighboring cells of the i -th cell.

Cell Cycle

Recent studies [34] have shown that many genes have a complex oscillatory function that depends on the metabolic cycle. In particular, it is known that cell growth can be limited by the amount of glucose in the G1 phase of the cell cycle. Studies in yeast show that there are independent metabolic oscillations in the control of the cell cycle that probably arise from a system of coupled oscillators [35]. In breast cancer, estrogen regulates the expression and function of cyclins, c-Myc, cyclin D1 and cyclin E-Cdk2 which are considered important in the control of G1/S phase progression [36, 37]. These studies suggest that there are molecular coupling mechanisms from metabolism to the cyclin/CDK system that govern the cell cycle. Cyclin E is known to show a periodic expression pattern during the G1 phase of the cell cycle. The levels of this cyclin increase during the late G1 phase and subsequently decrease in the S phase, leading to a significant increase in cyclin D. In the subsequent phases G2 and M of the cell cycle, cyclin D is degraded and cyclin E begins to increase again in the early G1 phase. Other CDK complexes, such as cyclins A and B, undergo periodic patterns opposite to those of cyclin E [37]. These antagonistic processes of the CDK complexes can be explained in terms of non-linear oscillations in which the maxima point to different phases of the cell cycle. Particularly, we could associate one of these maxima with the transitions of the G phases of the cell cycle [38].

Tissue and organ development are controlled by master mechanisms of cell cycle. For instance, transcription factors simultaneously upregulate differentiation of genes and CDKs inhibitors [39]. On the other hand, it has also been demonstrated that TNF- α and TGF- β factors regulate proliferation and apoptosis processes by controlling the cytokines in the cell cycle [40]. Taking this into account, here we consider that TNF- α and TGF- β regulate the cyclins E and B. These are the two key players responsible for the out-of-phase oscillations that drive the cell cycle. Therefore, we can think of the dimensionless Lotka-Volterra system of equations as the mathematical model that describes the cell cycle oscillations

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} &= u(1 - v), \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} &= \beta v(u - 1),\end{aligned}\quad (\text{A } 4)$$

where the functions $u(t)$ and $v(t)$ represent the concentrations of cyclins E and B, of a cell at time t , respectively. The wave shape solution depends only on the local parameter β and on the boundary conditions of each cell. This system of equations describes out of phase oscillations with dimensionless period $T = 2\pi/\sqrt{\beta}$.

Considering that each cell has a slightly different period due to variations of glucose local concentration, i.e. $\beta = \gamma c_i$ with γ an adjustable parameter that measures the cell glucose consumption. Now, we assume that locally c_i follows a normal distribution with mean c_0 . By applying the standardization method it can be scaled to the basal glucose concentration, c_0 , with mean zero and variance one. Then,

the cell clock cycle of each cell can be estimated as

$$T_i = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{\gamma c_i}} = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{\gamma(c_0 - (\langle c_i \rangle - c_i))}}. \quad (\text{A } 5)$$

By taking the first two terms of the Taylor series expansion of the square root and writing $\beta_0 = \gamma_0 c_0$, one obtains

$$T_i = T_0 \left[1 + \frac{\gamma_0}{2\beta_0} (\langle c_i \rangle - c_i) \right], \quad (\text{A } 6)$$

with $T_0 = 2\pi/\sqrt{\beta_0}$ the dimensionless phase oscillation of basal cells and $\langle T_i \rangle = T_0$. We considered a basal cell period of $T_0 \approx 36$ days [41]. Note that equation (A 6) shows that c_i fluctuations around the mean value yield either cell arresting or proliferation.

The transport of glucose is described by equation (A 3) where the elastic potential variations may change locally the amount of glucose in the cells. This fact can significantly change the reproduction cell clock cycle giving rise to an unbalance in the tissue. To take this into account we estimated the time derivative of the glucose fluctuations by taking the derivative of equation (A 6) and assuming that the number of cells is approximately constant in a period T_0 , then

$$\frac{dT_i}{dt} = \frac{\gamma_0 T_0}{2\beta_0} \left[\left\langle \frac{dc_i}{dt} \right\rangle - \frac{dc_i}{dt} \right] := \Delta c_i. \quad (\text{A } 7)$$

To estimate the cell clock cycle of each cell we solved equation (A 7) coupled to equation (A 3).

Differential equations for MGRN dynamics

We studied the MGRN (figure 2 in the main text) as a logical network motif that can be translated to continuous space as a set of delay differential equations. As suggested in Ref. [42], the logical set of interactions allows to faithfully capture the system regulatory steps.

Logic gates are natural functions used to describe biological networks, which have two inputs regulating a single output. The logic parameter space has two single-input functions: AND-type and OR-type [42]. The gates generate either, ON ("active") or OFF ("inhibitive") output depending on whether inputs are activators or inhibitors. Additionally, in a cooperative scheme, the sum of two Hill terms provides a form of fuzzy logic gates where the values of ϵ_i close to 1 simulate active inputs while values of ϵ_i close to 0 represent an inhibitive response. Therefore, from the attractors of the GRN in its Boolean form, we can estimate a set of ϵ_i values that leads to the GRN attractors in the

continuous space. The set of differential equations are

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{R}_{y_1} &= \epsilon_1 \left[\frac{1}{1+x_1^n} + \frac{1}{1+y_3^n} + \frac{1}{1+y_4^n} + \frac{1}{1+c_3^n} \right] \\
&\quad + \epsilon_1 \left[\frac{1}{1+(\hat{y}_1)^n} \right] - R_{y_1}, \\
\dot{y}_1 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{y_1})^m} - y_1, \\
\dot{R}_{y_2} &= \epsilon_2 \left[\frac{1}{1+y_1^n} + \frac{1}{1+y_2^{-n}} + \frac{1}{1+y_3^{-n}} \right] - R_{y_2}, \\
\dot{y}_2 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{y_2})^m} - y_2, \\
\dot{R}_{y_3} &= \epsilon_3 \left[\frac{1}{1+y_4^n} + \frac{1}{1+y_2^{-n}} \right] - R_{y_3}, \\
\dot{y}_3 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{y_3})^m} - y_3, \\
\dot{R}_{y_4} &= \epsilon_4 \left[\frac{1}{1+x_2^n} + \frac{1}{1+y_1^n} \right] - R_{y_4}, \\
\dot{y}_4 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{y_4})^m} - y_4, \\
\dot{R}_{c_1} &= \epsilon_5 \left[\frac{1}{1+(\hat{y}_1)^n} + \frac{1}{1+c_3^n} + \frac{2}{1+c_2^{-n}} \right] - R_{c_1}, \\
\dot{c}_1 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{c_1})^m} - c_1, \\
\dot{r}_1 &= \epsilon_6 \left[\frac{1}{1+c_2^{-n}} + \frac{1}{1+c_3^{-n}} \right] - r_1, \\
\dot{R}_1 &= \frac{1}{1+(r_1)^m} - R_1, \\
\dot{r}_2 &= \epsilon_7 \left[\frac{1}{1+c_3^n} + \frac{1}{1+c_4^{-n}} \right] - r_2, \\
\dot{R}_2 &= \frac{1}{1+(r_2)^m} - R_2, \\
\dot{R}_{c_2} &= \epsilon_8 \left[\frac{1}{1+R_1^n} + \frac{1}{1+R_2^n} \right] - R_{c_2}, \\
\dot{c}_2 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{c_2})^m} - c_2, \\
\dot{R}_{c_3} &= \epsilon_9 \left[\frac{1}{1+(\hat{y}_1)^n} + \frac{1}{1+c_2^{-n}} \right] - R_{c_3}, \\
\dot{c}_3 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{c_3})^m} - c_3, \\
\dot{R}_{c_4} &= \epsilon_{10} \left[\frac{1}{1+x_2^n} + \frac{1}{1+c_2^n} \right] - R_{c_4}, \\
\dot{c}_4 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{c_4})^m} - c_4, \\
\dot{R}_{z_3} &= \epsilon_{11} \left[\frac{1}{1+c_3^{-n}} + \frac{1}{1+c_2^n} + \frac{1}{1+c_1^{-n}} \right] \left[\frac{0.5}{1+z_3^{-n}} \right] - R_{z_3}, \\
\dot{R}_{z_4} &= \epsilon_{12} \left[\frac{1}{1+(\hat{y}_1)^n} + \frac{1}{1+(\hat{c}_3)^n} + \frac{1}{1+c_4^{-n}} \right] - R_{z_4}, \\
\dot{z}_3 &= \frac{1}{1+(R_{z_3})^m} - z_3, \quad \dot{z}_4 = \frac{1}{1+(R_{z_4})^m} - z_4,
\end{aligned}$$

where r_1 and r_2 are auxiliary functions that binarize the cooperative action of a logical function that contains more than two logical variables as is suggested in Ref. [42].

Geometric domain of epithelial cells in the acinar-ductal region

The acinar cell structure can be visualized as a U -shaped structure that we mathematically define in terms of the vector functions $\vec{\alpha}_i$ of the form

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{\alpha}_1(r, \theta, l) &= (r \cos \theta, r \sin \theta), \\
\vec{\alpha}_2(r, \theta, l) &= (-r, -l), \\
\vec{\alpha}_3(r, \theta, l) &= (r, -l), \\
\vec{\alpha}_4(r, \theta, l) &= (r, -l_0),
\end{aligned} \tag{A 8}$$

where r is the radius of the circular shape and is in the interval $r \in \{r_{min} = 2, r_{max} = 3\}$, $\theta \in (0, \pi)$ and the ductal length is $l \in (0, l_0)$ where $l_0 \in [1, \infty)$ represents the vertical shape. The parameter l is a model degree of freedom that allows us to estimate the inflammation of the system. The function $\vec{\alpha}_1$ represents a semicircular curve that symbolizes the curved part of the end of the canal and the beginning of the acinar group. The functions $\vec{\alpha}_2$ and $\vec{\alpha}_3$ represent the left and right sides of the ductal group, respectively. Finally, the function $\vec{\alpha}_4$ describes the lower part of the structure that encloses the ducts. Figure 1 shows the geometry and definition of the functions $\vec{\alpha}_i$, with $i = 2, 3, 4$. The geometry of the model allows us to calculate analytically the area in all regions and obtain the domain area A_T .

Considering that in an equilibrium configuration the acinar-ductal zone is composed of single-cell columns that occupy half of the domain radii, that is, $(r_{max} - r_{min})/2$, where r_{max} and r_{min} are the maximum and minimum radii, respectively (see figure 1). Then, one calculates the area, A_{cell} , occupied by the cells by considering that r_{in} (internal radius) and r_{out} (outer radius) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
r_{out} &= \left(\frac{r_{max} + r_{min}}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r_{max} - r_{min}}{2} \right), \\
r_{in} &= \left(\frac{r_{max} + r_{min}}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r_{max} - r_{min}}{2} \right),
\end{aligned} \tag{A 9}$$

then

$$A_{cell} = (r_{max} - r_{min}) \left[\frac{\pi}{2} (r_{max} + r_{min}) + 2l \right]. \tag{A 10}$$

Now, if the area A_{cell} contains N cells that compete for space, then the domain area, A_T , can be written as $A_T = A_{cell}(N - 1)/2N$ as a measure of profitability. Here, the numerator reflects an adjusted loss while the denominator tends to the initial value. The equation (A 10) indicates that the space is almost completely covered when $N \gg 1$, while when N is small, there is a free available space. Finally, one can write the domain area as

$$A_T = (r_{max} - r_{min}) \left[\frac{\pi}{2} (r_{max} + r_{min}) + 2l \right] \left(\frac{N - 1}{2N} \right). \tag{A 11}$$

Anti-inflammatory mechanisms in the system

The acinar-ductal system undoubtedly contains mechanisms that allow it to mitigate inflammation and maintain an adequate balance in cellular tissue. Considering this observation, we believe that there are two key metrics in our model that can be used to evaluate inflammation in this system: (i) the effective area of the domain A_T , and (ii) the basal cell size represented by its Voronoi area, \hat{A}_{cell} . Thus, we define an inflammation indicator I by comparing the theoretical area for N cells at time t with the domain area, that is

$$I(N, t) = \frac{A_T(N, t)}{\hat{A}_{cell}(N, t)}. \quad (\text{A } 12)$$

This indicator allows one to recognize situations in which the geometric domain introduces pressure on the cells ($I = A_T/\hat{A}_{cell} > 1$), which as pointed out in the text, translates into an inflamed system because it does not have enough space to relax. On the other hand, when ($I = A_T/\hat{A}_{cell} < 1$), cells are relaxed since they have enough space to move and stabilize. Considering this, we propose two mechanisms to mitigate inflammation in the acinar-ductal system:

i) *Elongation of the ductal canal depending on the Voronoi area and the geometric domain area.* When there is growth, there is a decrease in both, the area as a function of cell density and perhaps the plasticity of the acinar-ductal system. Therefore, we proposed to lengthen the area of the ductal canal of the structure to reduce inflammation in the region and maintain an adequate balance in the tissue. This mechanism is activated when $I = A_T/\hat{A}_{cell} > A_{up}$ is satisfied, where A_{up} is the threshold and is typically less than one. In our case, we have taken $A_{up} = 0.9$ which represents a 10% tolerance. Thus, from equation (A 11) the elongation of the

ductal canal is calculated as follows

$$dl = \frac{\hat{A}_{cell}(N(t_0), t_0)}{(r_{max} - r_{min})} \left(\frac{N(t_0) + 1}{N(t_0)^2} \right), \quad (\text{A } 13)$$

where dl is the length to be added to the ductal canal, $\hat{A}_{cell}(N(t_0), t_0)$ is the total area occupied by the cells at time t_0 , and $N(t_0)$ is the total number of cells.

ii) *Fine adjustment of the ductal canal for sudden changes in the number of cells.* In the event that an accelerated increase in the number of cells occurs, an increase in the standard deviation of the area of the cells can be detected. To counteract this effect and mitigate inflammation, the rate of change of ductal length is adjusted. In such case, $I = A_T/\hat{A}_{cell} > A_{up}$ and the activation mechanism holds to ensure that cell density is conserved. The area change indicator Σ is defined as

$$\Sigma(t, t - \tau_0) = \frac{\sigma(t) - \sigma(t - \tau_0)}{\sigma(t - \tau_0)}, \quad (\text{A } 14)$$

where $\sigma(t)$ is the standard deviation of the cell area at time t , and τ_0 is the proliferation period. If the indicator Σ is outside the range given by the area increase thresholds, ($\Sigma_{min}, \Sigma_{max}$), an adjustment is made to the rate of change of ductal length. To maintaining a balance in the acinar-ductal system and mitigate inflammation in cellular tissue, we propose the ansatz: $\Sigma_{min} = -0.05$ and $\Sigma_{max} = 0.05$ for the thresholds, assuming a tolerance of 5%. To regulate cell density and preserve homeostasis in the tissue and/or considering sudden changes in the number of cells we adjusted the length of the duct. To this end, we consider two cases: a) *Inflammation:* $\Sigma(t, t - \tau_0) > \Sigma_{max}$, then the rate of change of the length dl of the acinar duct increases as $dl \rightarrow dl + \sigma(t) - \sigma(t - \tau_0)$; and b) *Relaxation:* $\Sigma(t, t - \tau_0) < \Sigma_{min}$, then the rate of change of the length dl of the acinar duct decreases slower than $dl \rightarrow dl + 0.5[\sigma(t) - \sigma(t - \tau_0)]$.

Figure 1. Domain configuration. r_{min} and r_{max} are the minimum and maximum radii of the domain, respectively. Further, r_{out} and r_{in} are the outer and inter radii occupied by the cells. The functions $\vec{\alpha}_i$ are defined in equations (A 8). l is the high of the ductal domain.

Table 1. Overview of genes and cytokines in the reduced genetic regulatory network of Pancreatic Cancer.

Gene/Protein	Full Name	General Information	Functions and Processes	References
TNF α	Tumor Necrosis Factor	This gene encodes a multifunctional proinflammatory cytokine involved in the positive regulation of hematopoietic stem cell differentiation, maintenance of intestinal epithelial structure, and response to bacteria.	Regulates cell proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, and lipid metabolism.	[43, 44]
TGF β 1	Transforming Growth Factor beta 1	This gene encodes a secreted ligand of the TGF- β family that regulates gene expression through the activation of TGF-beta receptors and SMAD transcription factors. It is frequently overexpressed in tumor cells.	Regulates cell proliferation, differentiation, and growth, and can modulate the expression and activation of other growth factors such as IFNG and TNF α .	[45–47]
KRAS	KRAS Proto-oncogene	Belongs to the RAS family, it encodes a GTPase protein. An activating mutation occurs in this gene, causing a change in a single amino acid, resulting in the formation of a transforming protein involved in various cancers. Cancer types include lung adenocarcinoma, mucinous adenoma, pancreatic ductal carcinoma, and colorectal carcinoma.	Cell proliferation and differentiation, signal transduction, and cell cycle regulation. Mutations promote the development of different types of cancer.	[48–51]
TP53	Tumor Suppressor Protein p53	This gene encodes a tumor suppressor protein that responds to cellular stress, regulating the expression of genes related to cell cycle arrest, apoptosis, senescence, and DNA repair. Mutations are associated with various types of cancer.	Induces DNA repair, cellular senescence, apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, and changes in metabolism.	[52–54]
PI3K (PIP3)	Phosphoinositide 3-Kinase	This gene encodes an isoform of the catalytic subunit of phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K or PIP3), a key enzyme in cell signaling and immune response in eukaryotic cells. It plays a crucial role in the activation of neutrophils at injury or infection sites. PI3K/AKT activation helps prevent apoptosis and promotes cell survival.	Cell growth, cell proliferation, apoptosis and cell survival regulator, cell migration, and metabolism.	[55–57]
MAPK1 (ERK)	Mitogen Activated Protein Kinase 1	This gene encodes a protein of the MAP family, also known as extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERKs). It participates in multiple cellular processes such as proliferation, differentiation, and transcriptional regulation. Its activation requires phosphorylation by kinases. In addition to its kinase function, it can act as a transcriptional repressor.	Proliferation, differentiation, cell development, transcriptional repressor, and regulator.	[58–60]
BCL-XL	B-Cell Lymphoma-Extra Large	It is an antiapoptotic protein of the BCL-2 family. It prevents the formation of lethal pores in the outer mitochondrial membrane, halts proapoptotic signals, inhibits cell death by interacting with p53 and VDAC1, and is involved in the regulation of cellular metabolism, autophagy, and mitosis.	Antiapoptotic protein involved in cellular regulation, metabolism, autophagy, cellular mitosis, and cell death regulation.	[61]
CDKN1A (P21)	Cyclin Dependent Kinase Inhibitor 1A	This gene inhibits the activity of CDK2(P33) and CDK4 to regulate the cell cycle in the G1 phase. Its expression is controlled by TP53 and is involved in cell cycle arrest due to stress. It participates in DNA replication in the S phase and DNA damage repair. Induced division by CASP activates CDK2(P33), triggering apoptosis.	Inhibits CDK2(P33) and CDK4, regulates cell cycle arrest and progression in the G1 phase, and participates in DNA replication and repair.	[62–64]
CASP (Caspase)	CysteinyI ASpartate Protease	Caspases (CASPs) are intracellular proteases that play a key role in apoptosis and tumor development. They also have roles in inflammatory response and other cellular processes. Mutations in CASPs can decrease their activity and promote the survival of cancer cells. Genetic variants in CASP-8 increase the risk of certain types of cancer. They can be regulated by transcription factors and other molecular mechanisms.	Involved in apoptosis, development of immune cells, cell cycle progression, and present in inflammatory responses. Regulates the survival of cancer cells.	[65–67]

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